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**SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO THE DETERMINATION OF
CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILL OF
PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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Annotation: This publication is devoted to the understanding of the nature of the systemic approach in pedagogy, which serves as a fundamental methodological basis for analysis and construction of the educational process. The historical roots of systemic thinking are studied, traced in the ideas of eminent thinkers such as Jan Amos Komenski, John Locke, Johann Friedrich Gerbart and Adolf Diesterwegh. Also mentioned is the contribution of domestic educators, in particular, Konstantin Ushinsky and Peter Kapterev. The key patterns of a systemic approach - integrity, hierarchy, structure and multidimensionality - and their practical application in education are examined. Special emphasis is placed on the didactic patterns that contribute to improving learning outcomes, as well as on the importance of the teaching team in light of Lydia Novikova’s concepts. The study concludes with a conclusion on the importance of a systemic approach to create a unified educational space and the comprehensive development of students’ personalities.

Keywords: system approach, pedagogy, educational system, didactic principles, educative process, integrity, hierarchy, structure, variability, collective education, educational environment, teaching methodology.

In today's fast-changing world, where educational systems are becoming increasingly complex, the need for science-based methods in teaching and education is urgent. The systems approach, as one of the key methodological directions in pedagogy, which became popular in the second half of the last century, solves this problem.

This approach views education as a single system consisting of interdependent parts operating under certain rules. Such a view allows us to understand more deeply the nature of pedagogical processes, see the links between different components, and develop better strategies for teaching and education.

The relevance of the systemic approach is dictated by the need to form a coherent picture of the world in students, encouraging their curiosity, autonomy and ability to make decisions. Therefore, the study of principles and ways of applying a systems approach in pedagogy is of great importance for both theory and practice.

MAIN PART

In pedagogy, the concept of a systemic approach began to be used extensively in the late 1960s. This approach is a scientific tool for studying complex objects. Its essence is to identify the main components that make up the object being studied, establish relationships between them, and determine the patterns of their functioning.

Therefore, the systems approach involves analyzing educational activities through the lens of systems theory. This theory studies complex objects called systems, which are characterized by a structure consisting of individual elements and parts and perform certain functions.

The formation of concepts aimed at a systemic perception of the educational environment is based on works by Western European thinkers, including Y.A. Komensky, D. Locke, I. F. Gerbarth and A. Diesterwegh. In the domestic pedagogical thought, the formation of ideas on system analysis takes its origin from

leading pedagogues such as K.D. Ushinsky, N.I. Pirogov, V.G. Belinsky, P.F. Kapterev, N.F. Bunakov, V.P. Wachter and other outstanding figures.

The systems approach is a segment of philosophical teachings and scientific methodologies, as well as an area of scientific knowledge and social activity. Its essence is to study subjects from the perspective of their systemic organization. Such an approach focuses researchers' attention on understanding the integrity of the object being studied, the key processes supporting this integrity, and on analyzing the diverse relationships between components of a complex object for integration into a single theoretical model. Systems methodology helps to correctly formulate scientific objectives in various fields of knowledge and develop the most productive ways to solve them.

A systematic approach requires the continual recognition and application of system-specific rules in knowledge and practice. The foundation of systemism is the material unity of the world and the dialectical laws of interrelation and development, which nevertheless undergo changes in different realms, acquiring unique forms in each type of system. It is important to highlight the key principles of a systemic approach:

- Integrity: Allows an object to be viewed as a whole and part of larger systems.
- Hierarchy: The presence of levels attached to each other, where elements of the lower order are subordinated to elements of the higher order.
- Structuring: Provides the ability to analyze individual components of a system and their interactions within a specific structure.
- Multiplicity: Provides an opportunity to use a variety of models (cybernetic, economic, mathematical) to describe both individual parts and the system as a whole.

The principles of a systems approach have found wide application in science, including pedagogy. In modern pedagogical practice, the concept of «system» has become one of the fundamental ones.

The systems approach in pedagogy facilitates isolation and thorough study of each system element independently. It allows you to analyze and compare these

elements, ultimately integrating them into a single whole. This process reveals their common features and differences, inherent contradictions and connecting features, the relative importance of some elements over others, and the development of both individual elements and the system as a whole.

The application of a systemic approach to training opens up wide opportunities for the use of various methodical techniques, organizational forms and pedagogical tools aimed at successful solving of educational problems. Such an approach fosters confidence in learners' abilities, develops motivation for success, and builds objective self-esteem.

The application of a systemic approach in educational practice is carried out by adhering to a number of didactic principles.

The principle of activeness emphasizes that students, not receiving information ready but actively exploring it, acquire a conscious understanding of the essence and forms of their educational activities. They accept established rules, participate in their development, which contributes to the formation of their common cultural, active and general educational skills.

The principle of continuity ensures that all stages of education are consistent, both in terms of content and methods, taking into account age-specific development patterns.

The principle of systematicity aims at forming a holistic, generalized vision of the world including nature, society, their own, as well as sociocultural aspects and spheres of activity.

The principle of optimal complexity and accessibility ratio (minimum) is to enable a student to acquire educational material at the highest possible level for him/her, corresponding to his/her area of immediate development, and at the same time ensure the absorption of the mandatory minimum established by the state standard.

The principle of psychological safety involves eliminating all stressors in the learning process, creating a welcoming atmosphere at school and in lessons based on cooperation and dialogue.

The principle of creative approach orients the educational process towards the development of creative potential and the acquisition by students of their own experience of research and creative activity.

This system of didactic principles allows children to transmit the cultural values of society while meeting the fundamental requirements of traditional pedagogy, such as visibility, accessibility, consistency, activeness and scientific validity of teaching.

L. I. Novikova emphasized that the principles of a systematic approach in the theory and practice of education are based on the concept of collective education. According to this approach, a key element of the education system is the educational collective, and the school education system as a whole should be seen as a set of interconnected groups. It becomes relevant to understand these ideas from the perspective of modern methodology, where education is treated as a process of soft impact. To integrate past experiences of collective education with new achievements, it is necessary to build on historical perspectives and modern concepts, forming a unified system that takes into account both existing and newly emerging data. It is important to find ways of developing the theory of collective upbringing in modern conditions.

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